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**QA4EO:: Support to cloud mask validation for CMIX
Operations and Validation Report**

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Table of contents

1. INTRODUCTION	4
1.1 OBJECTIVE	4
1.2 SCOPE	4
2. SKY CAMERA SETUP	5
2.1 INSTRUMENTATION	5
2.2 LOCATIONS	6
3. OPERATIONS	7
3.1 SETUP PHASE	7
3.1.1 SKY CAMERA DATA TRANSFER	8
3.1.2 EXTRACTION OF S2 AND L8 ACQUISITIONS	8
3.1.3 MATCHUP GENERATION BETWEEN S2, L8 AND SKY CAMERA IMAGES	10
3.1.4 PRE-PROCESSING OF SKY CAMERA DATA (CROP, FLIP, ROTATE)	10
3.1.5 FINDING AN APPROPRIATE CLASSIFICATION METHOD	12
3.1.5.1 Tested methods	12
3.1.5.2 Final preliminary method – random forest classifier	13
3.1.6 SAMPLE GENERATION AND CLASSIFIER TRAINING	14
3.1.7 SKY CAMERA IMAGE CLASSIFICATION AND SAMPLE EXTRACTION	16
3.1.8 CREATION OF PREVIEWS AND GEOTIFFS	17
3.1.9 CREATION OF CONFUSION MATRICES	19
3.2 OPERATIONAL PHASE	20
4. VALIDATION RESULTS	21
4.1 SKY CAMERA CLASSIFICATION VALIDATION	21
4.2 SC AUTOMATIC CLASSIFICATION	22
4.2.1 SENTINEL-2	22
4.2.2 LANDSAT 8	23
4.3 SC MANUAL CLASSIFICATION	24
4.3.1 SENTINEL-2	24
4.3.2 LANDSAT 8	24
4.4 COMPARISON BETWEEN RAP AND SC 2 (FERMI) RESULTS	25

5. LIMITATIONS	28
6. CONCLUSION	30

1. Introduction

1.1 Objective

The objective of QA4EO WP 2185 - Support to cloud mask validation for CMIX is to prepare for establishing and for operating a network of cloud mask validation sites. Based on the experience in Europe (Rome site – La Sapienza University) and the United States of America (Goddard site – Goddard Space Flight Center) a concept for instrumentation and operations will be developed and tested.

The goal is to prototype algorithms and methods to process data and compare them with satellite algorithms for cloud masking. A critical requirement is the cloud base. There are two approaches that have been planned to be compared: using stereo sky camera data (US) and a ceilometer (Rome). The Rome site was upgraded and received 2 sky cameras identical to the US site.

This WP should provide a proof-of-concept, delivering a plan for global upscaling. The main result of this task will be a report on the experiences of this experiment and the results of the cloud screening validation at the example of Landsat 8 and Sentinel 2 MSI. Additionally, a roadmap towards a global network will be developed.

1.2 Scope

The scope of this document is to document the test operation of the sky camera setup and to provide some initial validation numbers.

2. Sky Camera setup

2.1 Instrumentation

A set of two cameras (stereo pair) was setup at La Sapienza University in Rome. There is sky camera one named “Marconi” and sky camera two named “Fermi”. The cameras use a Raspberry Pi 4 and the Omnivision OV5647 sensor. The field of view is 194 (horizontal) and 142 (vertical). Distance between cameras is around 260 meters. Currently, the cameras are collecting data every minute between 08:00 and 14:00 UTC.

Sky camera two (Fermi) is located close to the ceilometer named RAP (Raymetrics Aerosol Profiler), to allow comparisons between the RAP and sky camera based cloud detection and to validate the sky camera based cloud high estimation with RAP measurements.

Besides the two sky cameras installed at La Sapienza University in Rome, there are two sky cameras with identical technical specifications installed at the Goddard Space Flight Center.

Figure 1: Sky Camera 1: Marconi

Figure 2: Sky Camera 2 – Fermi

Figure 3: Raymetrics Aerosol Profiler (RAP)

2.2 Locations

Figure 4: Locations of Fermi, Marconi and RAP

Below are the exact locations of the three instruments:

Sky cam 1, "Marconi"

41°54'10.6"N 12°30'47.7"E

41.902946, 12.513247

Sky cam 2, "Fermi"

41°54'05.4"N 12°30'56.7"E

41.901494, 12.515761

RAP

41°54'04.9"N 12°30'57.4"E

41.901352, 12.515932

3. Operations

3.1 Setup phase

The following steps have been executed during the setup phase:

- Implementation of data transfer of the Rome sky camera data form UoM to BC
- Setup of server and archive system to store the Rome sky camera data.
- Development of scripts to find matching Sentinel-2 (S2) and Landsat 8 (L8) data using the Euro Data Cube Service. Euro Data Cube is a partnership between industry leading companies, working together to reduce the gap between data and knowledge. The Service is supported by the European Space Agency (ESA).
- Development of scripts to find sky camera data matching the overpass time of S2 (L8) acquisitions.
- Development of pre-processing methods for the sky camera data to crop, flip and rotate the data to be matching the satellite acquisitions.
- Literature research, analysis of existing methods and development of a classification method for sky camera data to cloud, clear sky and sun.
- Generation of training samples to train a random forest classifier for the sky camera data, followed by training a random forest (RF) classifier for sky camera 1 and 2 of the Rome site.
- Implementation of the RF algorithm to classify the sky camera images and to extract samples for S2 and L8 validation
- Development of an algorithm to create overviews of the sky camera data and satellite data over the sky camera sites
- Development of a validation method to create confusion matrices between satellite cloud masks and classified sky camera data.
- Development of an algorithm to read RAP data and to create confusion matrices between RAP and sky camera classification

Finally, these developments have led to a prototype processor to semi-automatically (a few manual interactions are still necessary), generate validation results between cloud masks provided by S2 and L8 and the sky camera cloud masks (SCM). The workflow of the processing is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Validation workflow overview

The setup phase was characterized by multiple delays caused by the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. The first big delay was caused by delayed shipment of the sky cameras from the United States of America to Rome, Italy, which caused 8 month delay. Further delay was caused by the development of classification algorithm by UoM, also due to the pandemic situation. Unfortunately, the algorithm was not finished close to the project end. Thus, an own classification algorithm

was developed by Brockmann Consult. Nevertheless, this led to another delay of nearly 10 months. In addition, the sky cameras at the Goddard Space Fligh Center encountered some issues leading to the cameras being non-operational. The pandemic conditions prevented the UoM staff from accessing the sky cameras to fix the issue, leading to unavailability of US sky camera data for the project.

Figure 6: Planned project schedule (top) and final project schedule after adaption to delays (bottom)

3.1.1 Sky camera data transfer

The sky camera data are collected by UoM from La Sapienza University (LSU) using rsync. Afterwards the data is again transferred via rsync from UoM to a BC server. Due to the time difference between the US and Europe and rsync being executed only once a day, there is a delay of one day in the data availability. This means, data of day x are available at BC on day x+1. Since a direct data transfer between the LSU and BC cannot be implemented (data are property of UoM) this delay cannot be circumvented at this stage.

3.1.2 Extraction of S2 and L8 acquisitions

It was decided to use the Euro Data Cube (EDC) Service to query S2 and L8 data, due to availability of the complete S2 L2A and L8 L2 archive through the Sentinel Hub Service and the possibility to process the data directly within the service (in the cloud) and to extract data cubes of required subsets for further processing. Using a cloud solution reduces processing times drastically, since download of complete S2 and L8 data is not required and for longer time series the data is directly available and does not need to be restored e.g. from the S2 archive from Copernicus Open Access Hub. Additionally, the data can directly be pre-processed (spatial subset, band subset, and queries on the data itself), drastically reducing the necessary time for downloading and processing and space required for storage.

The final matching data is stored in an AWS S3 bucket in a data cube in ZARR format (example shown in Figure 7).

Objekte (19)

Objekte sind die grundlegenden Entitäten, die in Amazon S3 gespeichert sind. Sie können [Amazon S3 Inventory](#) verwenden, um eine Liste aller Objekte in Ihrem Bucket abzurufen. Damit andere auf Ihre Objekte zugreifen können, müssen Sie ihnen explizit Berechtigungen erteilen. [Weitere Informationen](#)

Objekte nach Präfix suchen

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	▲	Typ	▼	Letzte Änderung	▼	Größe	▼	Speicherklasse	▼
<input type="checkbox"/>	.zattr		zattr		17.02.2022 04:50:40 PM CET		3.1 KB		Standard	
<input type="checkbox"/>	.zgroup		zgroup		17.02.2022 04:50:37 PM CET		24.0 B		Standard	
<input type="checkbox"/>	.zmetadata		zmetadata		17.02.2022 04:50:56 PM CET		16.6 KB		Standard	
<input type="checkbox"/>	B02/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	B03/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	B04/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	B08/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	B11/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	B12/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	CLD/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	CLM/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	CLP/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	lat/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	lon/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	SCL/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	time_bnds/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	time/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	viewAzimuthMean/		Ordner		-		-		-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	viewZenithMean/		Ordner		-		-		-	

Figure 7: Extracted datacube in ZARR format in AWS S3 bucket

The developed scripts allow to query the data. The user can select sensor (S2 or L8), bands, resolution, and start/end date for the required satellite data and to setup a bounding box for the area to be queried. For this exercise the area was limited to the location of the sky cameras of the Rome site.

Besides the storage of the spatial subsets in ZAR format in the S3 bucket, information of the pixel matching the SC location is extracted and stored in a CSV file. The method can additionally be adjusted to extract a 3x3, 5x5 or 7x7 pixel window. The CSV file holds all data for the complete time series between the defined start and end date (see Figure 8).

time	B02	B03	B04	B08	B11	B12	CLD	CLM	CLP	SCL	lat	lon	time_bnds	join_ID	
14.02.2021 10:09	0.0581	0.0652	0.0788	0.1038	0.1953	0.157	0	0	0	52	5	41.90285	12.51325	14.02.2021 10:09	20210214
19.02.2021 10:09	0.111	0.1294	0.14	0.1694	0.2072	0.1608	0	0	13	5	41.90285	12.51325	19.02.2021 10:09	20210219	
24.02.2021 10:09	0.0786	0.0991	0.1112	0.1416	0.2056	0.1621	5	0	0	91	5	41.90285	12.51325	24.02.2021 10:09	20210224
01.03.2021 10:09	0.1106	0.1256	0.1522	0.1964	0.2143	0.1767	0	0	0	42	5	41.90285	12.51325	01.03.2021 10:09	20210301
06.03.2021 10:09	0.4584	0.4244	0.486	0.4588	0.4572	0.4166	100	1	1	253	9	41.90285	12.51325	06.03.2021 10:09	20210306
11.03.2021 10:09	0.1264	0.1428	0.1744	0.2166	0.237	0.1895	0	0	0	16	5	41.90285	12.51325	11.03.2021 10:09	20210311
16.03.2021 10:09	1.1592	1.0408	1.0088	1.0032	0.2767	0.3078	0	1	1	255	8	41.90285	12.51325	16.03.2021 10:09	20210316
21.03.2021 10:09	0.2962	0.2966	0.322	0.3716	0.3724	0.3769	98	1	1	248	9	41.90285	12.51325	21.03.2021 10:09	20210321
26.03.2021 10:09	0.0694	0.0627	0.0604	0.0663	0.0774	0.0609	0	1	1	79	2	41.90285	12.51325	26.03.2021 10:09	20210326
31.03.2021 10:09	0.1642	0.178	0.2194	0.2728	0.2897	0.2743	0	0	0	26	5	41.90285	12.51325	31.03.2021 10:09	20210331
05.04.2021 10:09	1.4072	1.32	1.2128	1.2584	0.6896	0.5825	100	1	1	255	9	41.90285	12.51325	05.04.2021 10:09	20210405
10.04.2021 10:09	0.98	0.9496	0.9592	0.9936	0.5453	0.4603	100	1	1	254	9	41.90285	12.51325	10.04.2021 10:09	20210410
15.04.2021 10:09	1.0336	0.9232	0.8896	0.948	0.6526	0.5637	100	1	1	255	9	41.90285	12.51325	15.04.2021 10:09	20210415
20.04.2021 10:09	0.1674	0.1902	0.2266	0.2818	0.2786	0.2497	0	0	0	36	5	41.90285	12.51325	20.04.2021 10:09	20210420
25.04.2021 10:09	0.1722	0.1968	0.2338	0.2954	0.3126	0.2742	0	0	0	44	5	41.90285	12.51325	25.04.2021 10:09	20210425
30.04.2021 10:09	0.1756	0.2024	0.2352	0.2836	0.2825	0.2494	0	0	0	40	5	41.90285	12.51325	30.04.2021 10:09	20210430
05.05.2021 10:09	0.183	0.21	0.253	0.3078	0.329	0.2845	0	0	0	89	5	41.90285	12.51325	05.05.2021 10:09	20210505
10.05.2021 10:09	0.1804	0.2142	0.2504	0.2972	0.2789	0.242	18	0	0	28	5	41.90285	12.51325	10.05.2021 10:09	20210510
15.05.2021 10:09	0.2046	0.2364	0.2742	0.3164	0.3427	0.2817	0	0	0	214	5	41.90285	12.51325	15.05.2021 10:09	20210515
20.05.2021 10:09	0.189	0.2166	0.251	0.3012	0.291	0.2459	0	0	0	16	5	41.90285	12.51325	20.05.2021 10:09	20210520
25.05.2021 10:09	0.204	0.2322	0.2698	0.3182	0.3376	0.2875	0	1	1	91	5	41.90285	12.51325	25.05.2021 10:09	20210525
04.06.2021 10:09	0.18	0.2012	0.244	0.2852	0.3055	0.2477	0	0	0	60	5	41.90285	12.51325	04.06.2021 10:09	20210604
09.06.2021 10:09	0.173	0.2032	0.247	0.288	0.2677	0.213	28	1	1	109	5	41.90285	12.51325	09.06.2021 10:09	20210609
14.06.2021 10:09	0.1676	0.2072	0.2338	0.2902	0.3353	0.2884	0	0	0	33	5	41.90285	12.51325	14.06.2021 10:09	20210614
19.06.2021 10:09	0.1446	0.1734	0.193	0.2466	0.2368	0.1965	36	0	0	29	8	41.90285	12.51325	19.06.2021 10:09	20210619
24.06.2021 10:09	1.388	1.2472	1.172	1.1864	0.2565	0.3016	0	1	1	255	8	41.90285	12.51325	24.06.2021 10:09	20210624
29.06.2021 10:09	0.694	0.6424	0.606	0.6276	0.2133	0.2464	0	1	1	255	8	41.90285	12.51325	29.06.2021 10:09	20210629
04.07.2021 10:09	0.1808	0.2032	0.2194	0.2624	0.2276	0.196	43	1	1	248	8	41.90285	12.51325	04.07.2021 10:09	20210704
09.07.2021 10:09	0.1734	0.2122	0.2548	0.2968	0.3399	0.2625	0	1	1	79	5	41.90285	12.51325	09.07.2021 10:09	20210709
14.07.2021 10:09	0.2276	0.2598	0.295	0.2934	0.3277	0.273	51	1	1	129	5	41.90285	12.51325	14.07.2021 10:09	20210714
19.07.2021 10:09	0.1798	0.2048	0.2536	0.2918	0.3236	0.2553	0	0	0	39	5	41.90285	12.51325	19.07.2021 10:09	20210719
24.07.2021 10:09	0.1548	0.1806	0.2198	0.262	0.2973	0.2542	0	0	0	43	5	41.90285	12.51325	24.07.2021 10:09	20210724
29.07.2021 10:09	0.1614	0.1896	0.2314	0.2834	0.3056	0.2418	0	0	0	43	5	41.90285	12.51325	29.07.2021 10:09	20210729
03.08.2021 10:09	0.1814	0.2162	0.2532	0.3066	0.3448	0.309	0	0	0	63	5	41.90285	12.51325	03.08.2021 10:09	20210803
08.08.2021 10:09	0.184	0.2226	0.254	0.2878	0.3079	0.2638	0	0	0	95	5	41.90285	12.51325	08.08.2021 10:09	20210808
13.08.2021 10:09	0.2224	0.2282	0.238	0.3172	0.3202	0.2734	31	1	1	15	5	41.90285	12.51325	13.08.2021 10:09	20210813
18.08.2021 10:09	0.1728	0.2064	0.2402	0.284	0.3017	0.2514	10	0	0	93	5	41.90285	12.51325	18.08.2021 10:09	20210818

Figure 8: Example of S2 L2A extractions of 1x1 pixel window stored in a CSV file

3.1.3 Matchup generation between S2, L8 and sky camera images

In a next step matchups are generated between the satellite acquisitions stored in the data cube and the complete sky camera archive. For this task, scripts have been developed that analyse the satellite acquisition dates stored in the data cube and matching sky camera acquisitions are selected from the sky camera archive. The sky camera archive holds acquisitions of both sky cameras taken with a temporal resolution of 5 minutes. Therefore, quite a big number of sky camera acquisitions need to be queried. The ones closest to the satellite acquisition are selected and copied to a working directory for further processing. This process can be done for each sky camera (SC) separately or for both SCs in parallel.

After this step all matching sky camera images with 0.05, 0.1, and 0.5 exposure times are stored in a separate place for subsequent processing, as shown in the example in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Example of matching sky camera images stored in a working directory

3.1.4 Pre-processing of sky camera data (crop, flip, rotate)

The matching SC images show the complete FOV of the camera, which is quite a lot geometrically distorted outside of the centre. Additionally, the upper part of the image does not represent north, since the SCs are installed looking a bit northwest. Furthermore, compared to the satellite acquisitions, the images are flipped left to right, since the camera is looking from the ground upwards and the sensor has the opposite. Figure 10 shows a comparison between a Sentinel-2 acquisition and the corresponding complete SC image flipped left to right. The example shows the drastic distortion caused by the fisheye lens and the difference in orientation.

Figure 10: Comparison between Sentinel-2 image and complete SC image (flipped horizontally)

To compensate for all this, methods have been developed and implemented in Python, to crop the image to the centre part, which is less affected by distortion, flipped horizontally and then rotated to match the cardinal directions properly and to allow direct comparison with the satellite data.

Figure 11: Example of raw (upper left) and pre-processed SC image (upper right) of SC1-Marconi, compared to a S2 acquisition of 05.05.2021 (upper centre). Overlay with two different transparencies (lower left and centre) compared to the S2 acquisition (lower right), for 05.05.2021

The examples shown in Figure 11, also show that distortion and differences in viewing geometries and directions between SC and satellite sensor, pose quite a big challenge for matching the observed clouds.

It was also analysed if the distortion of the fisheye lens can be corrected. Nevertheless, the results at this stage have not been satisfactory and will be revisited in a potential second phase of the project.

In addition, the use of the three different exposure times was investigated to create High Dynamic Range (HDR) images. First test showed good results (see Figure 12), but also some problems leading to quite unusable images.

Figure 12: Example of a good HDR image (right) created from the three exposures 0.05 (left), 0.1, 0.5.

Figure 13: Example of bad HDR images

Therefore, this method was also discarded for later refinement. A decision was made to start with low exposure images for further processing.

3.1.5 Finding an appropriate classification method

It was not intended to develop a classification method for the sky cameras within the scope of the project. But due to the prior described pandemic induced delays, a solution needed to be found. In Autumn 2021 it was decided to try to develop and implement an own classification if no classification was available until October 2021

Literature research on basic RGB image classification and sky camera classification has been conducted.

3.1.5.1 Tested methods

A few methods have been tested that have not led to required accuracies. These methods included:

- Simple threshold on a greyscale representation of the RGB image
- Otsu thresholding
- Otsu thresholding after Gaussian filtering
- Implementing a linear light filter, to enhance the contrasts in the images to improve the results of the prior three methods
- Brightness index (BI), Sky index (SI) method by Letu et al. 2014

Figure 14 to Figure 16 show examples of a SC image and classification results from Otsu thresholding after Gaussian filtering and the BISI method. Both methods lead to extreme commissioning errors of clear sky as cloud. Otsu without Gaussian filtering and a simple global threshold on greyscale images led to even worse results.

Figure 14: SC 1 image 26.03.2021

Figure 15: Classification using Otsu threshold after Gaussian filtering

Figure 16: Classification using BI SI method from Letu et al. 2014

3.1.5.2 Final preliminary method – random forest classifier

Since none of these methods had reached the necessary accuracies, it was tested if a random forest (RF) classifier can be trained for each camera, to achieve the necessary quality in classification. First tests with only a small set of samples had already shown quite promising results. Therefore, it was decided to train two RF classifiers, one for each SC. Separate classifiers have been trained since the characterization of the instruments does not seem to be precise enough to use a single classifier for both.

3.1.6 Sample generation and Classifier training

To implement the RF classifiers, training data had to be generated first. 12 to 15 SC images per SC have been selected. Polygons representing the same class have been drawn on the SC images (see Figure 17 lower left). Inside these polygons random samples have been generated (see Figure 17 lower right). Overall 11,100 samples for SC1 and 27,300 samples for SC 2 have been collected.

Figure 17: Training sample generation. SC image (top), training polygons (lower left), training samples (lower right)

The collected samples have been used to train two separate RF classifiers. Figure 18 and Figure 19 show the same SC image as for the other classification results and the results from the RF classifier. Even though there are some smaller omissions and commissions, the overall accuracy is quite high and much better compared to the previously tested methods.

Figure 18: SC 1 image 26.03.2021

Figure 19: Classification using RF classifier

The following classes have been trained:

- 0 = Clear
- 10 = NoData
- 50 = Sun
- 100 = Thin clouds (cirrus)
- 255 = Opaque clouds

3.1.7 Sky camera image classification and sample extraction

Using the trained RF classifiers, a python based tool has been developed to classify the prior identified SC images matching the satellite acquisitions. The classification information of the centre pixel and the majority vote of a 7x7 pixel window around the centre is then extracted and stored in a CSV file.

date	time	skycam_class	skycam_class_window
20210214	101002	0	0
20210219	101002	0	0
20210224	101002	0	0
20210301	101002	0	0
20210306	101002	255	255
20210311	101002	0	0
20210316	101002	255	255
20210321	101002	255	255
20210326	101002	255	255
20210331	101002	0	0
20210405	101002	255	255
20210410	101002	255	255
20210415	101002	255	255
20210420	101002	0	0
20210425	101002	0	0
20210430	101002	0	0
20210505	101002	0	0
20210510	101002	0	0
20210515	101002	0	0
20210520	101002	0	0
20210525	101002	0	0
20210604	100902	0	0
20210609	100902	255	255
20210614	100902	255	255
20210619	100902	100	100
20210624	100902	255	255
20210629	100902	255	255
20210704	100902	100	100
20210709	100902	0	0
20210714	100902	255	255
20210719	100902	0	0
20210724	100902	0	0
20210729	100902	0	0
20210803	100902	0	0
20210808	100902	0	0
20210813	100902	255	255
20210818	100902	255	255

Figure 20: Example of extracted classification results stored in a CSV file

For this phase of the project the extraction of centre information was chosen since the differences in viewing geometries could not be solved properly.

3.1.8 Creation of previews and geotiffs

For a better understanding of later results and for visual analysis, previews of all SC images (see Figure 21) and corresponding satellite data (see Figure 22) are automatically generated. Additionally, the time series of satellite data stored in the data cube is converted to single geotiff files for each acquisition for further use.

Figure 21: Example of 4 generated SC previews (SC2) of 05.05.2021 (top left), 10.05.2021 (top right), 25.05.2021 (bottom left), and 09.06.2021 (bottom right)

Figure 22: Example of 4 generated Sentinel-2 L2A previews of 05.05.2021 (top left), 10.05.2021 (top right), 25.05.2021 (bottom left), and 09.06.2021 (bottom right)

3.1.9 Creation of confusion matrices

In a final step, a tool has been developed to generate confusion matrices between the sky camera classifications (used as reference) and the satellite cloud mask (product to be validated). This tool harnesses the satellite data extractions and sky camera classification extractions stored in a csv file, joints the data based on dates, and automatically plots confusion matrices, as shown in Figure 23.

Sky Camera 2 automatic classification vs. Sentinel-2 L2A SCL (8', 9, '10)

		Sky Camera 2				
		Clear	Cloud	Sum	U A	E
Sentinel-2 L2A	Class					
	CLEAR	27	5	32	84.4	15.6
	CLOUD	2	12	14	85.7	14.3
Sum		29	17	46		
P A		93.1	70.6		OA:	84.78
E		6.9	29.4		BOA:	81.85

Scotts Pi: 0.659
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.663
 Cohens kappa: 0.661

Figure 23: Example confusion matrix

3.2 Operational phase

There is nothing major to report from the operation phase since development of methods have been done quite late in the project, due to all delays described in the beginning of this document.

The main activity within the operational phase was the creation of the validation results. Nevertheless, this was at no time a complete operational activity since developments and adaptations have been done in parallel.

The only thing operational over the whole project time was the data transfer of the sky camera data from LSU, to UoM to BC, which is running smoothly since February 2021, with some smaller interruptions. After some rsync issues, caused by UoM servers, scripts for monitoring incoming data at BC have been put in place. If data is not coming in for two consecutive days a warning is raised and UoM will be contacted via email to check the transfer.

The latest update concerning the GSFC SC data was sent on 22.02.2022 stating "The cameras at Goddard still need a final network migration before they are both completely operational." Thus, the GSFC data will be usable within a potential second phase of the project.

In context of CMIX II preparations, UoM have stated that the SC network has been extended to six SC sites:

- GSFC, Greenbelt, Maryland, USA
- Wisconsin, USA
- Sapienza University, Rome, Italy
- Valencia University, Valencia, Spain
- Sao Paulo University, Sao Paulo, Brazil
- Antarctica¹

Another part of the project would have been the comparison between cloud height estimated with the stereo sky cameras and the cloud bottom height of the RAP. Nevertheless, the algorithm for cloud height estimation from SC data has not been provided by UoM within the project time. Therefore, the short operational time was used to compare clouds identified by the RAP and clouds identified by SC 2 Fermi, which is located 22m apart from the RAP.

¹ <https://geog.umd.edu/feature/umd-skycam-project-deploys-sky-imagers-antarctica>

4. Validation results

In this section validation results will be presented. In a first step the automatic classification of the SCs was validated against a manual classification done on the SC images, to evaluate the classification performance. Afterwards Sentinel-2 and L8 data have been validated against the automatic and manual classification. In a last step the classification of SC 2 (Fermi) and the RAP was compared.

4.1 Sky camera classification validation

The classification of the sky camera data needs to achieve a very high accuracy to be able to be a reference source for validation. Therefore, the centre pixel of the SC data was classified manually and compared to the automatic classification results.

SkyCam 1 manual classification vs. SkyCam 1 auto classification

		Sky Camera 1 manual classification				
Sky Camera 1 automatic classification	Class	Clear	Cloud	Sum	U A	E
	CLEAR	30	2	32	93.8	6.2
	CLOUD	2	27	29	93.1	6.9
	Sum	32	29	61		
P A	93.8	93.1		OA:	93.44	
E	6.2	6.9		BOA:	93.45	

Scotts Pi: 0.868
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.869
 Cohens kappa: 0.868

Figure 24: Validation results for Sky Camera 1 Marconi

SkyCam 2 manual classification vs. SkyCam 2 auto classification

		Sky Camera 2 manual classification				
Sky Camera 2 automatic classification	Class	Clear	Cloud	Sum	U A	E
	CLEAR	38	1	39	97.4	2.6
	CLOUD	1	26	27	96.3	3.7
	Sum	39	27	66		
P A	97.4	96.3		OA:	96.97	
E	2.6	3.7		BOA:	96.85	

Scotts Pi: 0.937
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.937
 Cohens kappa: 0.937

Figure 25: Validation results for Sky Camera 2 Fermi

The validation results for SC 1 and 2 show very strong agreements between the automatic and manual classification of overall accuracy (OA) between 93.44 and 96.97. Additionally, the distribution of the reference between cloud and clear is quite even distributed. Therefore, the interpretation of commission and omission error is reliable, leading to a balanced overall accuracy (BOA) close to the OA. The tendency of omission and commission error is equal for cloud and clear. The classification of SC2 performs quite a bit better compared to SC1. When taking the number of training samples into account, this might be due to the fact that less training samples have been collected for SC1. This could be improved in a potential second phase of the project. The difference in the number of total samples is caused by the fact that only cloud and clear observation from the sky camera have been regarded. Observations where the classification has returned “thin/cirrus cloud” (value 100) has been disregarded.

This high agreement shows that the sky camera classification delivers a reliable source for validation.

4.2 SC automatic classification

4.2.1 Sentinel-2

Figure 26 and Figure 27 show the validation results for Sentinel-2 L2A scene classification cloud mask (values 8,9 and 10, see Figure 28) against SC1 and SC2 automatic classification. The OA is between 86% and 88%. These numbers are quite comparable with the validation results of sen2cor during the CMIX exercise.

Sky Camera 1 automatic classification vs. Sentinel-2 L2A SCL (8', 9, '10)

		Sky Camera 1			U A	E
Class	Clear	Cloud	Sum			
CLEAR	35	7	42	83.3	16.7	
CLOUD	2	24	26	92.3	7.7	
Sum	37	31	68			
P A	94.6	77.4		OA:	86.76	
E	5.4	22.6		BOA:	86.0	

Scotts Pi: 0.728
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.73
 Cohens kappa: 0.729

Figure 26: Sentinel-2 SCL validation results using SC1 automatic classification

'Sky Camera 2 automatic classification vs. Sentinel-2 L2A SCL (8', 9, '10)

		Sky Camera 2			U A	E
Class	Clear	Cloud	Sum			
CLEAR	36	5	41	87.8	12.2	
CLOUD	3	23	26	88.5	11.5	
Sum	39	28	67			
P A	92.3	82.1		OA:	88.06	
E	7.7	17.9		BOA:	87.2	

Scotts Pi: 0.751
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.753
 Cohens kappa: 0.752

Figure 27: Sentinel-2 SCL validation results using SC2 automatic classification

Label	Classification
0	NO_DATA
1	SATURATED_OR_DEFECTIVE
2	DARK_AREA_PIXELS
3	CLOUD_SHADOWS
4	VEGETATION
5	NOT_VEGETATED
6	WATER
7	UNCLASSIFIED
8	CLOUD_MEDIUM_PROBABILITY
9	CLOUD_HIGH_PROBABILITY
10	THIN_CIRRUS
11	SNOW

Figure 28: L2A scene classification classes

4.2.2 Landsat 8

Figure 29 and Figure 30 show the validation results for Landsat 8 L2 BQA cloud mask (Bit 3) against SC1 and SC2 automatic classification. The OA is between 78% and 80%. These numbers are quite comparable with the validation results of LaSRC during the CMIX exercise for the PixBox dataset.

Sky Camera 1 automatic classification vs. Landsat 8 QA (Bit 3)
Sky Camera 1

Landsat 8 L2	Class			U A	E
	Clear	Cloud	Sum		
CLEAR	16	5	21	76.2	23.8
CLOUD	2	10	12	83.3	16.7
Sum	18	15	33		
P A	88.9	66.7		OA:	78.79
E	11.1	33.3		BOA:	77.8

Scotts Pi: 0.561
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.567
 Cohens kappa: 0.564

Figure 29: Landsat 8 QA validation results using SC1 automatic classification

Sky Camera 2 automatic classification vs. Landsat 8 QA (Bit 3)
Sky Camera 2

Landsat 8 L2	Class			U A	E
	Clear	Cloud	Sum		
CLEAR	13	5	18	72.2	27.8
CLOUD	1	11	12	91.7	8.3
Sum	14	16	30		
P A	92.9	68.8		OA:	80.0
E	7.1	31.2		BOA:	80.85

Scotts Pi: 0.598
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.604
 Cohens kappa: 0.605

Figure 30: Landsat 8 QA validation results using SC2 automatic classification

4.3 SC manual classification

4.3.1 Sentinel-2

Figure 31 and Figure 32 show the validation results for Sentinel-2 L2A scene classification cloud mask (values 8,9 and 10) against SC1 and SC2 manual classification. The results for SC1 completely match those of the automatic classification, while the results for SC2 differ a tiny bit. This was a bit surprising, since the initial validation of the automatic classification presented in section 4.1 has shown a higher precision for the automatic classification of SC2. We will come back to this and show an explanation for this difference in section 5.

Sky Camera 1 manual classification vs. Sentinel-2 L2A SCL (8', 9, '10)'

		Sky Camera 1 manual			U A	E
Sentinel-2 L2A	Class	Clear	Cloud	Sum		
	CLEAR	35	7	42	83.3	16.7
	CLOUD	2	24	26	92.3	7.7
	Sum	37	31	68		
P A	94.6	77.4		OA:	86.76	
E	5.4	22.6		BOA:	86.0	

Scotts Pi: 0.728
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.73
 Cohens kappa: 0.729

Figure 31: Sentinel-2 SCL validation results using SC1 manual classification

Sky Camera 2 manual classification vs. Sentinel-2 L2A SCL (8', 9, '10)

		Sky Camera 2 manual			U A	E
Sentinel-2 L2A	Class	Clear	Cloud	Sum		
	CLEAR	37	5	42	88.1	11.9
	CLOUD	3	24	27	88.9	11.1
	Sum	40	29	69		
P A	92.5	82.8		OA:	88.41	
E	7.5	17.2		BOA:	87.65	

Scotts Pi: 0.759
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.761
 Cohens kappa: 0.759

Figure 32: Sentinel-2 SCL validation results using SC2 manual classification

Figure 33 and Figure 34 show the validation results for Landsat 8 L2 BQA cloud mask (Bit 3) against SC1 and SC2 manual classification. The numbers for the manually classified SC data are a bit higher compared to the automatic classified results. The OA is between 81% and 84%.

4.3.2 Landsat 8

Sky Camera 1 manual classification vs. Landsat 8 QA (Bit 3)

		Sky Camera 1 manual			U A	E
Landsat 8 L2	Class	Clear	Cloud	Sum		
	CLEAR	14	6	20	70.0	30.0
	CLOUD	0	12	12	100.0	0.0
	Sum	14	18	32		
P A	100.0	66.7		OA:	81.25	
E	0.0	33.3		BOA:	83.35	

Scotts Pi: 0.623
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.629
 Cohens kappa: 0.636

Figure 33: Landsat 8 QA validation results using SC1 manual classification

Sky Camera 2 manual classification vs. Landsat 8 QA (Bit 3)

		Sky Camera 2 manual			U A	E
Landsat 8 L2	Class	Clear	Cloud	Sum		
	CLEAR	13	5	18	72.2	27.8
	CLOUD	0	14	14	100.0	0.0
	Sum	13	19	32		
P A	100.0	73.7		OA:	84.38	
E	0.0	26.3		BOA:	86.85	

Scotts Pi: 0.687
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.692
 Cohens kappa: 0.694

Figure 34: Landsat 8 QA validation results using SC2 manual classification

4.4 Comparison between RAP and SC 2 (Fermi) results

Figure 35 shows the comparison results (confusion matrix) between the RAP and the closest sky camera, SC 2 (Fermi). The results show a comparable low agreement (below 80%). This result was a bit surprising.

Sky Camera 2 automatic classification vs. RAP cloud top

		Sky Camera 2				
		Clear	Cloud	Sum	U A	E
RAP	Class					
	CLEAR	19	5	24	79.2	20.8
	CLOUD	3	11	14	78.6	21.4
Sum		22	16	38		
P A		86.4	68.8		OA:	78.95
E		13.6	31.2		BOA:	77.6

Scotts Pi: 0.559
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.565
 Cohens kappa: 0.56

Figure 35: Comparison between RAP and SC2 automatic classification

Since the automatic classification of SC 2 seemed to be a bit less good performant, the RAP data was compared to the manually classified SC2 data, to ensure highest classification accuracy for SC2. As shown in Figure 36 the agreement increased to above 84% OA. Nevertheless, the agreement was lower then expected.

SkyCam 2 manual classification vs. RAP

Sky Camera 2 manual classification for RAP position

		Clear	Cloud	Sum	U A	E
RAP	Class					
	CLEAR	20	3	23	87.0	13.0
	CLOUD	2	8	10	80.0	20.0
Sum		22	11	33		
P A		90.9	72.7		OA:	84.85
E		9.1	27.3		BOA:	81.8

Scotts Pi: 0.65
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.656
 Cohens kappa: 0.651

Figure 36: Comparison between RAP and SC2 manual classification

Table 1 shows the matching results between SC2 (skycam_class) and the RAP quality flag (QF) for cloud top height. The red marked entries show disagreements in the classification. The sky camera data for those dates have been analysed.

Table 1: Table with merged SC2 manual classification and RAP QF results

	date	time_x	skycam_class	RAP_QF
0	20210316	101002	255	11
1	20210321	101002	255	11
2	20210326	101002	0	0
3	20210405	101002	255	11
4	20210410	101002	255	11
5	20210415	101002	100	11
6	20210420	101003	0	0
7	20210425	101002	0	0
9	20210430	101002	0	0
11	20210505	101002	0	0
12	20210510	101002	0	0
13	20210515	101002	255	0
14	20210520	101002	0	0
15	20210525	101002	0	0
16	20210604	100902	0	0
17	20210609	100902	0	11
18	20210614	100902	0	0
19	20210619	100902	255	0
20	20210624	100903	255	10
21	20210629	100902	255	10
22	20210704	100902	100	10
24	20210709	100902	0	0
26	20210714	100902	255	0
28	20210719	100902	0	0
29	20210724	100902	0	0
30	20210729	100902	0	0
31	20210803	100902	0	11
32	20210808	100902	0	0
33	20210813	100902	100	10
34	20210818	100902	0	0
35	20210823	100902	100	0
36	20210828	100902	0	11
37	20210902	100902	0	0
38	20210907	100902	0	0
39	20210917	100902	255	11
40	20210922	100902	0	0
42	20210927	100902	255	0

Figure 37 shows the location of the SC2 acquisition at the centre pixel, where the two red lines (horizontal and vertical) meet. The SC has detected a cloud, while the RAP QF showed clear sky. This was done for multiple images where there was no match between the two instruments. The most likely explanation is the location difference of 22m between the two instruments. The RAP is located 22m toward north northeast of SC2. A red/green cross in Figure 37 marks the potential location of the RAP acquisition within the SC image.

Figure 37: Location of SC2 centre pixel (crossing of long red lines) and potential location of RAP acquisition (red/green cross)

The potential location of the RAP acquisition has been manually classified for all SC2 data, to ensure a “true” comparison between the two instruments. Figure 38 shows the agreement between the RAP QF and the manual SC classification for the potential RAP location. Now the results show an agreement above 93% OA.

SkyCam 2 manual classification vs. RAP
 Sky Camera 2 manual adjusted classification for RAP position

Class	Clear	Cloud	Sum	U A	E
	CLEAR	21	2		
CLOUD	0	9	9	100.0	0.0
Sum	21	11	32		
P A	100.0	81.8		OA:	93.75
E	0.0	18.2		BOA:	90.9

Scotts Pi: 0.854
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.856
 Cohens kappa: 0.855

Figure 38: Comparison between RAP and SC2 manual classification adjusted for location difference

5. Limitations

Geometric issues

To eliminate the bias from the S2 L2A scene classification and to compare clouds visible in the satellite image and the sky camera, a subset of the above used S2 data was manually classified for the SC1 location. Figure 39 show the results for the comparison. The OA is still below 90%. Therefore, the question arose why there is no better agreement.

Sentinel-2 L2A cloud mask over SkyCam 1 manual L1C classification

		In-Situ Database				
Class		Clear	Cloud	Sum	U A	E
Sentinel-2 L2A	CLEAR	24	5	29	82.8	17.2
	CLOUD	0	14	14	100.0	0.0
	Sum	24	19	43		
	P A	100.0	73.7		OA:	88.37
	E	0.0	26.3		BOA:	86.85

Scotts Pi: 0.754
 Krippendorfs alpha: 0.757
 Cohens kappa: 0.757

Figure 39: Comparison between manually classified S2 data and manually classified SC1 data

S2 products and SC1 (as well as SC2) data for cases without matching classifications have been compared. Figure 40 and Figure 41 show the results of this comparison. The images show that the cloud in the centre of SC2 (Fermi) is located northeast of SC2 in the S2 L2A image. While the same cloud is located southwest of the centre of SC1 (Marconi) and south/over SC1 in the S2 L2A product. The cause for this mismatch can be explained by the viewing differences of the three instruments and the location of the cloud above ground. The S2 L2A data have been acquired off-nadir with a VAA mean of 130.28053 and a VZA mean of 3.3807745. The purple arrow in the left images indicate the viewing direction of the S2 sensor. The parallax between true nadir and the actual S2 location cause the cloud to be projected in north-western direction onto the ground.

Figure 40: Comparison between SC acquisitions and S2 L2A data. Google Earth overview with SC1 and SC2 location (top left), S2 L2A RGB (bottom left), SC1 image (top right), and SC2 image (bottom right). The purple arrow in the left images indicate the viewing direction of the S2 sensor.

Figure 41: S2 L2A RGB, bigger window size. The purple arrow in the left images indicate the viewing direction of the S2 sensor.

Figure 42 illustrates the potential differences of cloud location between a satellite sensing off-nadir and the nadir view of the sky camera. This difference can lead to an incomparability of the data. A solution to fix this issue needs to be analysed during a potential second phase of the project.

Figure 42: Schematic illustration of potential viewing differences between a satellite sensor and a sky camera acquisition

This geometric mismatch also explains the non-linear difference between the validation results of the initial SC validation, the automatic SC classification validation, and the manual SC classification validation results, since the location of the clouds in the S2 products varies with each acquisition (VZA, VAA) and cloud height.

6. Conclusion

The results from the experimental operations had shown that the sky camera data provide an interesting and valuable reference source for comparison. The strength of the data is the constant acquisition (leading to a dataset with a high temporal resolution), quite high classification accuracy that could be achieved by the RF classifier, the comparable low costs for the instrument.

While the validation or better intercomparison results had shown a quite good agreement between the SC classification and the satellite (S2 & L8) cloud masks, the study had also revealed geometric issues that can lead to incomparability between SC and sat data. Further studies are needed to analyse if these issues/disagreements can be circumvented/corrected.

7. References

Letu, Husi & Nagao, Takashi & Nakajima, Takashi & Matsumae, Yoshiaki. (2014). Method for validating cloud mask obtained from satellite measurements using ground-based sky camera. *Applied Optics*. 53. 7523-7533. 10.1364/AO.53.007523.